

1 **NKG7 functions in establishment of tolerance in the immune system.**

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6 This study describes involvement of the activation marker NKG7 in multiple transplant biology settings and
7 expression of the natural killer cell marker in the immune system. NKG7 expression marked the self
8 non-self interface at the epithelial barrier in patients with sclerotic-type chronic graft versus host disease
9 (GVHD). NKG7 was highly activated in the tissues in solid organs transplant patients: in heart during
10 acute rejection following transplant and in bronchoalveolar lavage in lung transplant recipients undergoing
11 acute rejection. In the immune system, we found enrichment of NKG7 in KIR2DL3+ cells. Together with
12 recent description of KIR2DL3 as a cognate ligand for HLA-V, a class I MHC receptor that specifically
13 marked transformed (cancerous) cells, the data described participation of activated natural killer cells in
14 KIR2DL3:HLA-V dependant surveillance activity that also involves the gamma delta T cells (Tyd). We
15 discovered functions for the natural killer cell marker NKG7 in tolerogenic functions associated with
16 homeostatic self non-self discrimination that are disrupted in stem cell and solid organ transplant patients
17 and in elimination of transformed cells associated with tumor surveillance.
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